

Comparison of Bidirectional DC/DC Converter Topologies for the More and All Electric Aircraft

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Abstract

DC/DC isolated converters allowing a bidirectional flow of energy between High-Voltage (HV) DC and Low-Voltage (LV) DC networks have been proposed to be integrated in future on board power distribution systems. These converters must meet the stringent efficiency and power density requirements that are typical of the aeronautic industry. This makes it especially challenging to determine which converter topology is best suited for each particular application. This work presents a thorough review of several topologies of bidirectional DC/DC power converters that are considered good candidates to meet certain important aeronautic requirements, as those related with high efficiency and high power density. We perform simulations on virtual prototypes, constructed by using detailed component models, and we optimized them following design criteria that are in accordance with those typically imposed by aeronautic requirements. This comparative analysis is aimed to clearly identify the advantages and drawbacks of each topology. As an outcome, we point out the topologies that, for the required power level at the chosen switching frequencies, yield higher efficiency in the whole range of required operation points and that are expected to allow more important weight reductions.

Introduction

As a consequence of the increase in electric power generation and distribution, trends in modern power distribution systems are toward an increase in voltage, with the aim of increasing efficiency and decrease the weight of the energy distribution system. In particular, one of the preferred proposed solutions consists on replacing the current distribution power system, based on a three-phase 115VAC or 230VAC at 400 Hz (or variable frequency on more modern aircrafts such as the Boeing 787 or Airbus 380), for a high-voltage DC distribution system (HVDC). Proposed HVDC nominal voltages are 270 VDC or 540 VDC, ie ± 270 VDC [1]. The development of a new electric power system based on HVDC creates the need to design a new generation of power converters to supply electrical power to the avionic loads of the aircraft, which typically require a low voltage 28VDC bus. Bidirectional power converters are also strongly linked to power management in aircraft applications with Electrical Storage Systems (ESS) [2].

In the mentioned context, this paper focuses on the key aspects of the design of power converters enabling bidirectional power transfer between a HVDC network and avionics 28VDC buses. In particular, we will focus on suitable topologies for ≈ 3 kW bidirectional isolated power transfer between 270VDC/28VDC. Since stringent aeronautic requirements make it necessary to achieve a high degree of optimization, we have decided to limit voltage range as much as possible, respecting voltage ranges defined in MIL-STD-704 standards.

The main contribution of this study is to merge the aspects listed below:

- Study of a wide set of relevant topologies for HVDC/LVDC application.

- Efficiency optimization in a wide voltage input and output operation range defined by specific aeronautic standards, as well as wide load range.
- Switching frequency considered in this study is oriented to high power density designs.

Analysis of chosen topologies

The main goal of the present study is to compare power topologies with different modulation techniques, for a particular application, under similar conditions, and assess the impact of recent technologies on their performance. Based on the literature review of potential topologies that might better suit our application, we have chosen five topology/modulation solutions: Dual Active Bridge (DAB) with Phase Shift modulation (PS) and modified Triangular Trapezoidal modulation scheme (TT) [3]; three phase version of DAB (DAB-3p); Active Bridge Active Clamp (ABAC) and Full Bridge Current Doubler topology (CD). These topologies are represented in Fig. 1.

Single phase DAB (Fig. 1a), either with PS or TT modulation schemes, as well as DAB-3p (Fig. 1b) feature voltage sourced ports interfacing both HV and LV bridges. Power transfer is based on setting a controlled AC voltage to AC inductor in series with the transformer. Single phase DAB-PS modulation does not guarantee Zero Voltage Switching (ZVS) in the HV bridge switches for certain converter operating points [3]. For this reason, in [3], extended triangular-trapezoidal modulation scheme (TT) is presented as an alternative modulation scheme aimed to improve performance without complicating excessively the implementation of the modulator. In the TT scheme, not only the phase shift between bridges is controlled, but also each bridge duty cycle.

Large rms currents in capacitors is one of the main

disadvantages of DAB-PS and DAB-TT, [3]. By contrast, in DAB-3p topology, these AC currents are much lower than in single phase DAB topologies, and the ripple frequency is six times the switching frequency (f_s), instead of twice f_s , thus leading to lower filtering requirements for DAB-3p. Moreover, although DAB-3p only allows PS modulation, its components stress is lower than in single phase DAB topologies, partly due to the higher components count.

Fig. 1: Schematics of considered topologies. (a) DAB; (b) Three-phase DAB; (c) CD; (d) ABAC.

ABAC (Fig. 1d) can be considered a variant of DAB-PS, in the sense that its operation principle is based in power transfer through the transformer series AC inductor, and it implements PS modulation. On the other hand, there are some differences with DAB in the LV side. In first place, transformer turns ratio is typically a half of that for DAB. Besides, LV components currents change between buck and boost modes. Voltage sourced half bridges are floating, instead of a full bridge connected to the LV bus, and LV floating buses voltage is twice the LV bus voltage. Finally, a DC inductor is connected to the output of each LV half bridge. One of the main advantages of ABAC compared to DAB-PS is the ripple cancellation of the two DC inductors at the LV ports [4], which would lead to lower filtering requirements if LV voltage regulation was not required.

Current doubler topology (Fig. 1c) is current sourced in the LV side, whereas the HV side sets a controlled voltage at the output of LV switching block through the transformer [3]. The transformer leakage inductance value is not essential for the converter operation. Still, having a certain inductance in this kind of LV current sourced topologies extends ZVS range in the HV side in buck mode [5]. On the other hand, if transformer leakage inductance is too large, it leads to an increase of rms currents in the converter, so a trade-off has been reached in this study. An important feature of CD topology is that it only presents one switch in the LV side, instead of a full bridge. Another important feature is the comparatively high LV MOSFETs turn-off voltage in boost mode. Thus, LV switches voltage must be clamped after turn-off, during the transient in which leakage inductor current equals the difference of DC inductor currents.

Regarding filters, there are certain differences in their structure of the different topologies. Since all the analysed topologies are voltage sourced in the HV side, all of them include a thin film capacitor bank (C_{1a}). In the LV side, though, there are differences between topologies. In DAB-based topologies, a ceramic capacitor bank (C_{2a}) directly interfaces LV bridge. In ABAC, each floating DC link of LV half bridges is also made of ceramic capacitors (C_{LV1} , C_{LV2}). In CD, since LV bridge is current sourced, no HF capacitors have been considered in the LV side. Capacitors represented in the LV buses of Fig. 1c and Fig. 1d are electrolytic capacitors included mainly for voltage regulation purposes.

Fig. 2: Complete converters filter structure. HF LV filter block is not required in ABAC and CD topologies.

Selection of components and losses models

Topologies performance greatly depend on the technology on their components. In order to get the maximum achievable performance of each topology for the most recent technologies, loss models of several state-of-the-art component technologies have been developed.

Particularly, a comparative analysis on several HV switches performance (SiC MOSFET, Si MOSFET with low on resistance and Si MOSFET with low reverse recovery) reveals that the use of SiC MOSFETs will lead to optimal performance in all the topologies. Since HV DC link has the same voltage for all the considered topologies, selected MOSFETs are suitable for all topologies. Unlike at the HV side, the voltage rating of the LV switches depends on the topology. Moreover,

since LV side handles high currents, MOSFETs parallelization is required to reduce both conduction and switching losses. Four Si MOSFETs per switch have been chosen as the best feasible solution for all the topologies, except for CD that requires eight MOSFETs per switch to keep low the losses in LV switches.

Detailed components losses models are then developed in order to evaluate efficiency at all the operating points of the optimization domain. In particular, the switching losses are modelled as a function of switched current and voltage, and conduction losses are modelled based on components datasheets. Custom magnetics models losses as a function of switching frequency, voltage and current waveforms are also used in this study.

Control aspects

First of all, it is convenient to indicate that the focus of this work is on topology and power electronics considerations. Due to that, the control techniques proposed in this work are based on frequency response of the discretized and linearized converter model. In our analysis, both filtering and control capability requirements are taken into account. For this purpose, we have implemented additional passives to the essential components, as shown in Fig. 2. In all the topologies and at both HV and LV sides, at least a DC inductor is required for current control, for short circuit current regulation capability. Note that, unlike for the other topologies, LV inductors are essential for topology operation for CD and ABAC. Moreover, HF capacitors in bridge DC links are designed to ensure a minimum voltage ripple. Still, a minimum value for the bridge capacitance has been considered for control reasons and also because a certain filtering capability for frequencies below switching frequency is required. DC inductor current control has been designed to achieve desired cut-off frequencies of $\sim 1.5\text{kHz}$. We have imposed that resonance of DC inductors with C_{1a} and C_{2a} (when existing) is in the order of ten times the desired current control cut-off frequency.

Results

In this section we compare efficiencies for the different converter topologies, focusing specially on the design at a switching frequency of 100kHz . The HVDC and LVDC voltage ranges are indicated in Table 1.

V1 (V)	V2 (V)	V1 _{nom} (V)	V2 _{nom} (V)	P _{nom}
[250,280]	[22,30]	270	28	3000

Table 1: Operating domain, based on MIL-704F standard. Nominal conditions definition

Firstly, efficiency has been calculated for the whole operating domain, based on losses estimation of the

main components. On the basis of that information, two kind of efficiency maps have been obtained. On the one hand, efficiency is calculated within both HV and LV ranges at full power (i.e. 3 kW), such as that one of DAB-PS topology in buck mode shown in Fig. 3. On the other hand, efficiency has been calculated when output power varies from half of full power to full power and input voltage varies within its operating range (see Table 1), keeping constant output voltage at its nominal value (see Table 1). An example of this kind of efficiency map is shown in Fig. 4. Analogous plots have been obtained for every topology and for both operational modes in both cases described.

Fig. 3: Efficiency map of DAB-PS at full power, in buck mode.

Regarding the analysis of efficiency at full power, it has been found that DAB topologies yield higher efficiency than ABAC and CD in buck mode. Particularly, DAB-3p and single phase (SP)-DAB with TT modulation exhibit the highest efficiencies, whereas CD yields the poorest result. In boost mode, DAB topologies have the same behaviour as in buck mode. Nevertheless, ABAC and CD topologies yield lower efficiency values in boost mode compared with buck mode. Efficiencies are also close to maximum values at nominal voltages in boost mode as well as in buck mode. As a final remark, we have checked that maximum losses in all topologies occur at full power. Thus, efficiency at full power has a special interest because it will determine heat sinking steady state requirements.

Fig. 4: Efficiency map of DAB-PS in buck mode, from half to full power, and nominal V2.

Regarding the analysis of efficiency at output nominal

voltage, it can be observed that the highest efficiency values are achieved by three phase-DAB and DAB with TT modulation in buck mode. CD yields the worst peak efficiency. Also, it is interesting to note that ABAC and DAB have similar efficiency patterns in the sense that for a given input voltage V_1 , efficiency decreases at higher powers. On the contrary, for the CD topology, efficiency dependency with power is negligible. Performance in boost mode is different than in buck mode. Such difference can be explained by the fact that, in the case of ABAC and CD, the performance of these topologies strongly depends on power transfer sign. The highest efficiency values in boost mode are reached by DAB-3p and DAB-TT topologies, while CD exhibits the worst performance again.

To complement efficiency results, we compare average losses (Fig. 5), calculated in the entire operating domain, of the five topologies studied. In those bar graphs, we represent total average losses and also the contribution of each type of loss: losses at essential magnetics, conduction losses at both voltage sides (HV cond. and LV cond.) and switching losses at both voltage sides (HV sw. and LV sw.).

Fig. 5: Average losses in % (converter losses divided by transferred power), including losses breakdown. (Upside) buck mode, (downside) boost mode.

A comparison of Fig. 5 (upside) and Fig. 5 (downside) reveals that for most topologies there exist no significant difference between average efficiencies when comparing buck and boost modes of operation. An exception is the CD topology, which shows a significant asymmetry in performance, that can be explained by the important difference in waveforms when only power sign is changed.

Since power density is one of the main constraints in the design of power converters for aeronautical

applications, expected weights of the five topologies analysed have been compared. Fig. 6 shows a weight comparison for the 100kHz design. The total weights are broken down into the contributions of the different passive considered in this study. Regarding this, the "DC ind." label stands for the contribution of the DC inductors that are required for topology operation in CD and ABAC topologies. "LV filter" and "HV filter" labels refer to high frequency capacitors required for the DC links that interface bridges, and OTS DC inductors added for extended control and filtering purposes. Finally, labels "Transf." and "AC ind." make reference to the contribution of the transformer and the AC inductors.

Fig. 6: Topologies passives weight estimation at 100 kHz.

Summing up, for a switching frequency of 100kHz the total passives weight is estimated to go from ~560 g for DAB-3p to ~880 g in the case of ABAC. If we compare the weight estimations of the two topologies that, according with efficiency results, present the higher average efficiencies it can be seen that the passives weight of DAB-TT is estimated to be 220 g more (i.e., ~40% more) than that for DAB-3p.

Conclusions

In this work we have carried out a thorough comparison of those converter topologies that are good candidates for a bidirectional power converter linking a HV 270VDC bus and a LV 28VDC bus, which are of interest for developing advanced HVDC power distribution systems in more electrical and all electrical aircrafts. In this analysis, which has been conducted based on virtual prototypes with accurate models of components, an optimization in terms of efficiency within a wide operating range and passives weight has been carried out.

We have concluded that the best choice in terms of efficiency is DAB-TT, followed by DAB-3p with little difference. In terms of weight, at 100kHz switching frequency, DAB-3p is the best option. An additional advantage of DAB-3p compared to DAB-TT is its modulator simplicity and its much lower filtering requirements. This means that less additional passives for EMI filtering are expected to be required in DAB-3p

compared with other topologies. Taking all this into account, we conclude that DAB-3p is the most suitable topology for our particular application and design constraints.

It must be pointed out that for this comparative work, we focused on a very specific voltage range, and a particular power range (half power to full power) which is of interest for the aeronautical industry. In that sense, results can be generalized only within this framework.

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